

Editor's Report

The March newsletter contains several items of information and report that should be of interest to EPG members. Please note that the EPG has its own web page at <http://www.iop.org/IOP/Groups/EP/> which is regularly updated by Lucy Parkin.

Forthcoming meetings

The next meeting of the Group will be on Wednesday 24 April at The Institute of Physics and will comprise the Annual General Meeting followed by a lecture on volcanic dynamics.

The newsletter also contains a notice of a meeting in May on electromagnetic environments and health in buildings organised by Abacus Communications, in conjunction with the Universities of Bristol and Reading. This is an important issue which was addressed by several speakers at last year's Physics Congress in the conference co-sponsored by the EPG and Medical Physics Group on *The Physical Environment and Health*.

In June, there will be a meeting on *Transport of Bioaerosols*, co-sponsored by the Group – details on a later page.

Other news

The *European Journal of Physics* is planning a special issue on environmental physics. Review-type contributions are required by August 2002 for publication at the end of the year. For details, contact Dr. Nigel Mason, Department of Physics & Astronomy, University College London, Gower Street, London WC1E 6BT.

Finally, Physics Congress 2002 will be held at Brighton from 7-11 April. Congress will include eight scientific conferences, including CMD19/CMMP 2002, the Physics Expo, and a range of activities for students. See congress.iop.org

Article of April
Environmental Physics Group

Newsletter

March 2002

FORTHCOMING MEETINGS

Volcanic Dynamics Talk & EPG AGM Meeting

The 11th Annual General Meeting of the Environmental Physics Group will be held on **Wednesday 24th April 2002** at 5:45pm. The meeting will be held in the Phillips Room at the Institute of Physics' headquarters at 76 Portland Place, London.

Following the adoption of the new Constitution three years ago, there are elections this year for all three Group officers; Chair, Vice-Chair and Honorary Secretary. As Douglas Peirson is stepping down from the committee after many years of invaluable service, there is also a vacancy for an Ordinary committee member. Nominations, which shall be proposed by not less than two members of the Group and be accompanied by the written consent of the nominee, must be sent to reach the Honorary Secretary of the Group not later than twenty-eight days before the AGM.

Following the AGM, a talk on "**Dynamics of the Eruption of the Soufriere Hill Volcano, Montserrat**" will be given by Professor Steven Sparks, of the Geology Department at Bristol University, commencing at 6:30pm. The meeting will close with discussion and refreshments.

A limited number of EPG travel bursaries will be available to assist members of the EPG attending this meeting. Contact Peter Hodgson for further details.

I look forward to seeing you at the meeting.

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Electromagnetic Environments & Health in Buildings International Conference

Sponsored by:
QuantaPhonic Systems Group

In this highly technical world, employee working conditions are of increasing importance and the pressure to provide acceptable working environments means that employee health risks cannot be overlooked.

One of the most important potential health hazards in modern technical environments is electromagnetic fields. Can emissions emanating from our PC's, mobile phones and other electrical equipment affect our health?? What are current government standards and guidelines and do they protect us?? What should we do to protect ourselves legally??

The "**Electromagnetic Environments & Health in Buildings International Conference**" on 16th and 17th May 2002 at The Royal College of Physicians in London, will tackle these issues.

Leading national and international speakers from universities, hospitals and related industries have agreed to share their knowledge and research on this very emotive issue.

This conference will be important to anyone who has a direct involvement with health and productivity within the workplace.

For information and bookings, contact:

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REPORTS OF MEETINGS

The Transport of Bioaerosols

Wednesday 19 June 2002

Institute of Physics Headquarters, 76 Portland Place, London

Organised by

**The Environmental Physics Group, The Aerosol Society
and The British Aerobiology Federation**

Airborne biological particles, "bioaerosols", such as bacteria, viruses and fungal spores, play important roles in the spread of human, animal and plant diseases. Knowledge of the transport of bioaerosols is vital to understand and manage disease spread. The need to understand bioaerosol transport has become increasingly urgent, especially in the light of recent crises such as the Foot and Mouth epidemic, spread of genetically modified organisms, and current fears regarding the potential threat of microbiological agents used for bioterrorism.

The meeting will address bioaerosol transport and detection methods and will include talks on Foot and Mouth virus dispersal, genetically modified pollen and allergenic pollen.

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Environment and Sustainable Agriculture

Report of a half-day meeting organised by the EPG at the Institute of Physics on 31 October 2001.

The relation between the environment and sustainable agriculture is an issue of key importance in both the developed and developing worlds in the 21st century. An audience of 35 members of the EPG and guests participated in a stimulating discussion of this topic led by four intellectually challenging and well-illustrated lectures from leading British experts.

The meeting opened with a comprehensive overview of the sustainable use of water in agriculture from Professor Peter Leeds-Harrison of the Institute of Water and the Environment, Cranfield University at Silsoe. He outlined the problems of land degradation from salinity arising from the use and misuse of irrigation with examples ranging from the slow decline of Babylonian civilization to the current ecological catastrophe of the Aral Sea. He demonstrated several novel technologies and management strategies for minimising the use of water, both for growing crops and for desalinating salt-affected soils, ranging from the theoretical via those undergoing research trials to fully-functioning management systems.

He was followed by Dr. James Garratt from the Department of Agricultural & Environmental Science, University of Newcastle upon Tyne, who discussed recent advances in the modelling and management of pesticide use in European horticulture. He demonstrated three crop/climate interactions: intensive cropping of vegetables and tomatoes under temporary polytunnel greenhouse tunnels in Almeria, southern Spain (an area where groundwater is heavily mined for irrigation and to which many agrochemicals are being leached); rainfed field cropping of vegetables in northern Italy on heavy soils in which there is substantial lateral movement of herbicide and pesticide; and flower production (especially roses) in glasshouses in central Finland under conditions of low light intensity and substantial downward movement of pesticide to a permanently high water table. A key theoretical advance was the use of concept of fugacity, the tendency of a compound to leave one environmental compartment (e.g. the atmosphere) and enter another (the soil, or plant, or groundwater), to predict movement and degradation of pesticides in complex systems.

After a break for tea, Prof. David Scholefield, from the BBSRC Institute for Grassland and Environmental Research, North Wyke, Devon, demonstrated how environmental and economic models could be combined to optimise the use of fertilisers in animal-production systems based on grassland, so that output was maximised and losses, especially of fertilisers and animal leavings in solution to ground and surface waters, were minimised. The models included the costs and income from different forms of management *and* realistic estimates of the economic costs of any resulting environmental degradation.

Prof. David Fowler, from the NERC Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, Edinburgh, explained how the emission of greenhouse gases from agriculture to the atmosphere could be controlled, contrasting the properties, pathways in the atmosphere and the environmental and economic consequences of the oxidised (Nox) and reduced (NH₃) forms of nitrogen emissions.

A open discussion then followed, which was so lively, extensive and wide-ranging that the meeting ran over its scheduled duration by 30 minutes, closing at 17.30 hours.

Derek Rose

Environmental Physics in Totality: observations during an African eclipse

J. MILFORD

Lecture given to the EPG and the London and South-East Branch at the Institute of Physics on 9 January 2002

As part of a larger project to study the effect of a total solar eclipse on animal behaviour, Professor James Milford, of the Physics Department of the University of Zimbabwe, set up three automatic weather stations within the Mana Pools World Heritage Site close to the Zambesi River, which is the northern border of Zimbabwe with Zambia. The three automatic weather stations, which were up to two kilometres apart, were surrounded by different densities of vegetation typical of the area. At all three sites air and soil temperatures, air humidity and incoming radiation were measured every few seconds before being averaged over three or five minutes. In addition, at one of the sites, measurements were made of wind speed and direction, soil moisture and soil heat flux. Conditions for studying the effect of a solar eclipse on meteorological variables were ideal with cloud-less conditions on the day of the eclipse and on the previous and subsequent days, when measurements were also made. The automatic weather station measurements showed very similar diurnal variations of air temperature at the three sites and nearly identical maximum solar radiation for the three days. During the three-day period there was only a light wind. Each day the wind started blowing about 7.30 a.m. reaching a maximum of 1 m s⁻¹ near mid-day and then returning to zero by about 4.30 p.m.

The total eclipse on 21 June (the winter solstice) lasted 3 minutes 20 seconds centred on 1506 local solar time. On that day the incoming solar radiation was reduced over a three-hour period with zero solar radiation being measured at the time of the total eclipse, i.e. it became completely dark, compared to 440 W m⁻² at the same time on the previous and following days. This reduction in radiation caused a fall of 4°C in air temperature and at the same time the wind speed became negligible – about 2 hours earlier than on the other days. After the passing of the eclipse the air temperature and humidity increased to reach higher values than on the other days. The reduction in wind speed during the eclipse suggested a decrease in convective exchange during this period. If this resulted in a shallower convective layer during the eclipse, there would be a greater build-up of heat and water vapour within the convective layer when the sun's radiation again reached the earth's surface, which would explain the observed higher values of temperature and humidity. The observations of air and soil temperatures over the three days were also compared. At the end of each night it was found unexpectedly that the soil temperature at 20 mm was consistently higher than the air temperature. Estimation of the temperature at the soil surface showed that it was 2°C warmer than the air temperature – no explanation for this phenomenon could be put forward.

Photos and a professional video increased the pleasure of this presentation of a rare event seen and recorded under ideal conditions.

John Stewart

The Charles Chree Award 2001

Peter Woods of the National Physical Laboratory wins the Charles Chree medal and prize for his contributions to environmental metrology, in particular the detection and monitoring of atmospheric trace gases and air pollution.

Since the 1970s Peter Woods has pioneered the development of advanced spectroscopic techniques for measuring the atmosphere, and has successfully applied these measurements to the field. His work on remote-sensing technology to measure industrial pollution has included the development of differential absorption lidar (DIAL). This work established the National Physical Laboratory as the world leader in infrared DIAL technology and has resulted in improvements to pollution protocols for several industries worldwide.

Woods and his team have also been at the forefront of research on the depletion of stratospheric ozone. In measuring the stratosphere Woods has led international balloon-borne campaigns, and a new ground-based technique that involves a diode-laser spectrometer has been developed. His research on Fourier-transform spectrometers has contributed significantly to international measurement campaigns.

Woods and his team have developed and deployed a transportable interferometer to standardize measurements made at all the permanent sites within the Global Network for the Detection of Stratospheric Change. He has also taken the lead in developing lightweight laser spectrometers for the detection of trace gases involved in ozone depletion and climate change deployed on high-altitude aircraft and balloons.

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PhD Thesis Abstract

Instrumentation for Atmospheric Measurements

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Department of Meteorology, University of Reading, UK

September 2000

Small ions are part of the atmospheric aerosol spectrum, and study of ion-aerosol interactions is fundamental in atmospheric physics. Air ion physics and instrumentation are reviewed, including the historical context. A miniaturised Gerdien condenser for ion measurement, operating *in situ* to minimise inlet errors, is described. Two operating modes using independent current and voltage decay measurements are employed. A more sophisticated self-calibrating and fully programmable ion mobility spectrometer (PIMS), based on the same principles, is also discussed. Detailed analysis of error terms and application of new technology is demonstrated to greatly improve its capability. A variety of self-consistent experimental approaches, including ionisation and ion concentration instruments, is used to calibrate the new PIMS instrument.

In developing and characterising the individual components of the PIMS, favourable and unfavourable operating regimes are identified: this approach can also be applied to other aspiration ion counting techniques. Use of a sophisticated programmable electrometer permits compensation for leakage terms. Electrically-charged aerosol particles have been found to complicate the ion measurements. Consequently, conventional ion-aerosol theory, which neglects the particulate concentration, is thought to be incomplete. The polymodal ion mobility spectrum, is also found to influence the instrument's operation.

The classical theory for calculating air conductivity from voltage decay measurements is modified to take account of the ion mobility spectrum, and a new technique to obtain ion mobility spectra by inversion is presented. Ion mobility spectra are also derived using conventional ion current measurements, and the two methods of obtaining ion spectra from independent PIMS measurements are shown to be consistent. Development of the novel programmable ion instrumentation, in conjunction with consideration of the ion mobility spectrum, yields an improved and flexible approach to *in situ* atmospheric ion measurements.

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